

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D6.1 Report on the Development of the Innovative DSS Tool

VERSION 2.0

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Table of Contents

Project Information	2
Document Information.....	3
Document History	3
Table of Contents	5
List of Figures	7
List of Tables.....	9
Executive Summary	10
1. The DSS Tool Application	12
2. The Integrated Approach for the Tympaki Study Area	19
2.1. Socio-Economic Criteria.....	20
2.1.1. Cost - Benefit Analysis (CBA)	24
2.2. Environmental Criteria.....	28
2.2.1. Groundwater Quantity	28
2.2.1.1. Groundwater Modelling with FEFLOW.....	29
2.2.1.2. Creation of the Response Matrix.....	34
2.2.1.3. Optimization of Pumping Rates.....	34
2.2.2. Results of the Simulation - Optimization Algorithm	36
2.2.2.1. Optimum Pumping Rates for Href=6,25 m.....	43
2.2.2.2. Optimum Pumping Rates for Href=6,5 m.....	47
2.2.2.3. Simulation and Optimization – Situation for the Optimum Pumping Rates for Href=6.75 m	55
2.2.2.4. Simulation and Optimization – Situation for the Optimum Pumping Rates for 55	55
2.2.2.5. Discussion.....	58
3. Environmental Data Management System	59
3.1. Type of Database	59
3.2. Relational Database Management System	60
3.3. Design Features	61
3.4. Metabase: a Brief Overview	62
3.4.1. Browsing Data	62
3.4.2. Asking Questions	63
3.4.2.1. Simple Questions.....	64
3.4.2.2. Custom Questions with Notebook Editor.....	66

3.4.2.3 Advanced Questions in Native Query Editor	68
3.4.3. Dashboards, Collections, Pulses	69
Appendix	71
For $H_{ref}=6,25$ m	72
Run 1	72
Run 2	75
For $H_{ref}=6,5$ m	78
Run 1	78
Run 2	81
Run 3	84
For $H_{ref}=6,75$ m	87
For $H_{ref}=7$ m	88

List of Figures

Figure 1. FCM clustering output.....	16
Figure 2. GDP projection under Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios	21
Figure 3. Projected Irrigation demand and water allocation from groundwater (green) and Faneromeni reservoir (red) using climate change scenarios, population variation, agricultural water demand and projected water availability through WEAP model.....	21
Figure 4. Schematic approach of the main demand sites and water sources, and their interconnections in Tympaki and upstream Messara basin using WEAP model.....	22
Figure 5. Assessment of adaptation measures in agricultures and their effect on the water availability.....	22
Figure 6. Current and future dependence on agriculture	23
Figure 7. Irrigation water status analysis and prediction	23
Figure 8. SWOT analysis for the Tympaki basin regarding water use and availability	24
Figure 9. Flowchart of Bayesian Risk and cost-benefit risk analysis	27
Figure 10. Tympaki study site with all the wells along with the representative ones for each group.....	29
Figure 11. Pumping wells as introduced in the FEFLOW model	30
Figure 12. Observation wells with calibration – validation data available.....	31
Figure 13. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of calibration period.....	32
Figure 14. Current situation at the end of the wet period of the 10-year simulation.....	33
Figure 15. Current situation at the end of the dry period of the 10-year simulation.....	33
Figure 16. Hydraulic heads at the observation wells according to the current situation.....	34
Figure 17. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the dry period considering zero pumping rates	37
Figure 18. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the wet period considering zero pumping rates	37
Figure 19. Hydraulic head in the observation wells considering zero pumping rates.....	38
Figure 20. Optimum pumping rates for the dry season	45
Figure 21. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$	46
Figure 22. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$	46
Figure 23. Hydraulic heads in the observation wells considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$	47
Figure 24. Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first and second S-O runs for $H_{ref}=6.5m$	51
Figure 25. Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first, second and third S-O runs for $H_{ref}=6.5m$	51
Figure 26. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$	52

Figure 27.: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$	53
Figure 28. Hydraulic heads in observation wells when considering optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$	54
Figure 29. Sample visualization of temperature data as a table	63
Figure 30. Sample visualization of temperature data as a scatter-plot.....	63
Figure 31. Sample of summarizing data in a simple question	66
Figure 32. Sample of implementing a custom question (joining and filtering), through Notebook Editor	68
Figure 33. Sample of implementing an advanced question in Native Query Editor	69
Figure 34. Sample dashboard	70

List of Tables

Table 1. FCM algorithm input	15
Table 2. FCM algorithm output	15
Table 3. FCM algorithm parameter values of the current implementation	16
Table 4. Mean absolute error at the observation wells – validation results	31
Table 5. Results of the simulation model - Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the dry season when considering zero pumping rates.....	39
Table 6. Results of the simulation model - Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the wet season when considering zero pumping rates.....	40
Table 7. Response matrix for the dry season	41
Table 8. Response matrix for the wet season	42
Table 9. b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.25m$	43
Table 10. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.25m$	43
Table 11. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref}=6.25m$	44
Table 12. b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$	47
Table 13. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$	48
Table 14. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$	49
Table 15. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the third run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$	50
Table 16. Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for $H_{ref}=6.75m$	56
Table 17. Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for $H_{ref}=7m$	57

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

Deliverable D6.1, version 2 is part of Task 6.1 “Initial Development and Testing of an Innovative Decision Support System” (Lead TUC, participants: UPV, UFZ, IST-ID, CERTE and BU). The aim of the current document is to update D6.1 Version1 with the description of the Decision Support System tool (DSS tool) operation in its final form. The delivered DSS tool has been formed after testing several alternatives. The final selection was based on the fact that it is operational for all the case study sites and complies with the requirements that had initially been set. More specifically, a Fuzzy Web-DSS tool, that will be available to the interested parties, was developed. The fuzzy approach was the most difficult to fulfill, as it was quite time-demanding to test and conclude to the most suitable algorithm. Two different approaches were attempted with unsuccessful results, until reaching the third operational one. The DSS will aid groundwater managers in the sustainable management of groundwater resources, by enabling the comparison of different user defined scenarios. The tool results in the clustering of the study site areas that encounter with the same groundwater quantity vulnerability.

The document consists of three sections. In the first one, the operation of the DSS tool application is described. In the second section, there is the algorithm of the integrated approach that was developed for the Tympaki study site (the Greek site). In the third section, a description of a database that has been developed to act collaterally with decision support

procedures is presented. The database is not integrated in the DSS tool. However, it can play an assistive role by providing well-organized and accredited data. Sections two and three have been maintained the same as in D6.1, version 1, except few minor alternations.

1. The DSS Tool Application

The objective of Work Package (WP) 6 is to develop a Decision Support System tool to support decision-making for sustainable groundwater resource management. The decision support system is based on the capitalization of the surrogate models developed in Work Package 3. Since the development of the surrogate models is the objective of WP3, this section focuses on the description of the fuzzy clustering algorithm used for the scenario comparison and applicable to the Turkish, Greek and Spanish study areas. The DSS tool works in a fuzzy logic framework and is available through the web.

At this point, it is important to mention that the DSS tool is based on the surrogate models developed for each study site. The tool aims to classify the sites into six categories: very low, low, low to medium, medium to high, high and very high vulnerability. The characterization is based on the clustering results obtained by the Fuzzy Clustering Method described in the following subsection. The clustering algorithm uses as input the difference or absolute difference of the groundwater level between the scenarios selected by the user. The scenarios are defined by changing parameters related to precipitation, groundwater pumping, and simulation period. Thus, the output clusters define the areas based on the vulnerability of the groundwater level which reflects the results of the differences in climatic conditions and groundwater use at different time horizons. Based on this information, groundwater managers can make decisions about remediation actions related to groundwater use and apply them to areas in the same cluster. Therefore, a different strategy can be developed for areas in the same cluster.

In addition, a fully numerical model that incorporates the cost – benefit analysis and groundwater simulation and optimization was applied to the Tympaki study site. This approach is presented in Sections 2 and 3 and can serve for decision aiding, but it is not incorporated in the DSS tool, because radical modifications were needed to be made. Another reason why this algorithm is not used in the DSS tool is that it requires more detailed data and computation time. However, the cost-benefit analysis part of the algorithm was performed for the study areas with the available data. This analysis is informative in determining the percentage that each water resource should contribute to the water budget.

1.1. Fuzzy Clustering Method

Fuzzy clustering is a powerful unsupervised method for the analysis of data and construction of models. In many situations, fuzzy clustering is more natural than hard clustering. Objects on the boundaries between several classes are not forced to fully belong to one of the classes, but rather are assigned membership degrees between 0 and 1 indicating their partial membership. Fuzzy c-means clustering was first reported in the literature for a special case by Joe Dunn in 1974. The general case (for any m greater than 1) was developed by Jim Bezdek in his PhD thesis at Cornell University in 1973. Fuzzy C-means (FCM) is a data clustering technique in which a data set is grouped into N clusters with every data point in the dataset belonging to every cluster -to a certain degree. For example, a data point that lies close to the center of a cluster will have a high degree of membership in that cluster, and another data point that lies far away from the center of a cluster will have a low degree of membership to that cluster. The FCM algorithm calculates the cluster centers as weighted mean, where the weights are membership grades of the data points in the clusters.

Most of the clustering algorithms are based on minimizing an objective function to get the most compact clusters placed in dense regions of data. FCM is based on the minimization of the following objective function:

$$J_m = \sum_{i=1}^D \sum_{j=1}^N \mu_{ij}^m \|x_i - c_j\|^2,$$

where:

- D is the number of data points.
- N is the number of clusters.
- m is fuzzy partition matrix exponent for controlling the degree of fuzzy overlap, with $m > 1$. Fuzzy overlap refers to how fuzzy the boundaries between clusters are, that is the number of data points that have significant membership in more than one cluster.
- x_i is the i^{th} data point.
- c_j is the center of the j^{th} cluster.

- μ_{ij} is the degree of membership of x_i in the j^{th} cluster. For a given data point, x_i , the sum of the membership values for all clusters is one.

The algorithm performs the following steps during clustering:

1. Randomly initialize the cluster membership values, μ_{ij} .
2. Calculate the cluster centers:

$$c_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^D \mu_{ij}^m x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^D \mu_{ij}^m}$$

3. Update μ_{ij} according to the following:

$$\mu_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{\|x_i - c_j\|}{\|x_i - c_k\|} \right)^{\frac{2}{m-1}}}$$

4. Calculate the objective function, J_m .
5. Repeat steps 2–4 until J_m improves by less than a specified minimum threshold or until after a specified maximum number of iterations.

The inputs and outputs of the function that performs the fuzzy C-means clustering are presented in the Tables 1 and 2, below.

Table 1. FCM algorithm input

Input	Type	Description
Data	Matrix	Data set to be clustered, specified as a matrix with N_d rows, where N_d is the number of data points. The number of columns in data is equal to the data dimensionality.
Nc	Integer	Number of clusters to create, specified as an integer greater than 1.
Options	Vector	<p>Clustering options, specified as a vector with the following elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Option (1)</u>: Exponent for the fuzzy partition matrix, U, specified as a scalar greater than 1.0. This option controls the amount of fuzzy overlap between clusters, with larger values indicating a greater degree of overlap. • <u>Option (2)</u>: Maximum number of iterations, specified as a positive integer. • <u>Option (3)</u>: Minimum improvement in objective function between two consecutive iterations, specified as a positive scalar. • <u>Option (4)</u>: Information display flag indicating whether to display the objective function value after each iteration, specified as one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - True: Display objective function. - False: Do not display objective function.

Table 2. FCM algorithm output

Output	Type	Description
centers	matrix	Final cluster centers, returned as a matrix with N_c rows containing the coordinates of each cluster center. The number of columns in centers is equal to the dimensionality of the data being clustered.
U	matrix	Fuzzy partition matrix, returned as a matrix with N_c rows and N_d columns. Element $U(i,j)$ indicates the degree of membership of the j^{th} data point in the i^{th} cluster. For a given data point, the sum of the membership values for all clusters is one.
objFunc	vector	Objective function values for each iteration, returned as a vector.

The fuzzy C-means (FCM) algorithm takes as input the difference or absolute difference of the estimated values of each desired scenario and produces a map, representing the areas of the same cluster. (Figure 1). The number of clusters is the same for all study sites and was set at six to represent the six different vulnerability levels: very low, low, low to medium, medium to high, high and very high. However, the boundaries of each cluster are not identical in the different runs because they depend on the input values, i.e the groundwater level results. The parameter values of the FCM algorithm for the current implementation are listed in Table 3.

Figure 1. FCM clustering output

Table 3. FCM algorithm parameter values of the current implementation

Parameter	Value
Number of Clusters	6
Exponent for the fuzzy partition matrix, U	15
Maximum number of iterations	100
Flag	false

For each InTheMED study site there is a different tab, where the respective surrogate model can be executed based on the input parameters that are set by the user. The results are spatially represented data (maps) that are also extracted as .kml files and can be previewed in Google Earth geo-browser.

A comparison option between two different scenarios for the same case study site, in one split screen, is also provided. This is applicable for the Konya, Tympaki and Requena – Utiel study sites. For the Grombalia and the Guadiana basin study sites, regression models were developed and the user can be informed for the hydraulic heads in specific observation wells based on different climate change models.

Any interested user can have access through 3 different ways:

1. From the following link 147.27.70.139:80 a web interface of the application is accessible. Through this web-site, instant runs can be executed on-line and the tool can be used without the need of any installation.
2. A MATLAB standalone application is also available which is suitable for any interested user who does not possess a MATLAB license.
 - a. The user has to download and install the Windows version of the MATLAB Runtime for R2022b from the following link on the MathWorks website <https://www.mathworks.com/products/compiler/matlab-runtime.html>
 - b. It is also necessary to download the standalone application from the following link https://www.chenveng.tuc.gr/fileadmin/users_data/enveng/uploads/inthemed/KTGGB_Surrogate_Models.rar and run MyAppInstaller_web.exe which is in this folder in order to install the application on the preferred destination folder.
 - c. The application can be run by navigating to the destination folder.

All the necessary information is available here:

<https://www.chenveng.tuc.gr/en/research/research-projects/inthemed/-/innovative-and-sustainable-groundwater-management-in-the-mediterranean>

3. A MATLAB App which is suitable for MATLAB users. The user has to download and instal the application from the following link:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ESmZF7tK4e8c4fKv6jfd1dQ0m5K5Gxex/view?usp=drive_link

After installation, the application is available on the “APPS” tab at their MATLAB window.

2. The Integrated Approach for the Tympaki Study Area

The sustainable management of groundwater resources framework that is proposed for the Tympaki study site takes into consideration multiple criteria: socio-economic and environmental. The algorithm is based on the multi-criteria optimization approach, thus meaning the formation of more than one objective functions. These objective functions refer to the respective criteria: optimum socio-economic management, optimum environmental management in terms of groundwater quantity and optimum environmental management in terms of groundwater quality.

The optimization process is applied within iterative simulation runs of the study area model, therefore constituting a time-demanding procedure. Along with the non-linear nature of the problem, the model complexity and time needed are increased. Therefore, focus has been given on efforts to overcome these difficulties, in order to provide the model with as much automation as possible.

The simulation – optimization procedure refers to the separate simulation and optimization of each criterion that is taken into consideration. For each criterion, a different analysis is conducted according to its nature. This way, the optimum value for the examined scenario is obtained for each criterion. In the following sections, the simulation model and the optimization procedure for the selected criteria are described.

2.1. Socio-Economic Criteria

A socioeconomic approach was established for the area considering socioeconomic data analysis and Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios using a statistical model and the WEAP model to identify the dynamics of social factors (population, economy) and agriculture (production, efficiency) in terms of water availability and use. Basic socioeconomic indicators (population, GDP, agriculture production) in the region are explored and the future trends are determined considering three different climate change RCP scenarios and relative Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios (IIASA - International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis) e.g., Figure 2. The development of more specific socioeconomic indicators such as agricultural intensity, crops, and land use is also investigated. The indicators' projected development is examined combining climate change RCP scenarios with SSP and the associated projected water availability to provide the expected climate change effect in the socioeconomic context. Another significant indicator that was investigated under green socioeconomic development was the capacity of the reservoir located in the area of study. The task considered the climatic scenarios effect in the reservoir's capacity. The WEAP model and a statistical model, is used to provide the projections on socioeconomic factors and water availability (basin, reservoir) Figures 3 and 4.

In addition, an assessment of adaptation measures in agricultural activities was conducted to determine their effect on the water availability considering the three different climate change RCP scenarios. Figure 5 provides the average results of the assessment based on the three scenarios. Furthermore, the current and future dependence on agriculture was estimated based on the socioeconomic status of the area and the expected rural investments (Figure 6). The irrigation water status was as well examined (Figure 7) assessing the previous and current situation and estimating the future patterns based on the available water sources in the area. It is obtained that surface water from the reservoir and the expected connection with a nearby new one will provide the majority of irrigation water around 67%. Finally, a swot analysis (Figure 8) was performed for the basin in order to study the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of water use and availability in the area considering current practises and expected policy transformations. All the presented results were obtained through the WEAP model considering a prior collection, statistical analysis and interpretation of the data.

Figure 2. GDP projection under Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) scenarios

Figure 3. Projected Irrigation demand and water allocation from groundwater (green) and Faneromeni reservoir (red) using climate change scenarios, population variation, agricultural water demand and projected water availability through WEAP model

Figure 4. Schematic approach of the main demand sites and water sources, and their interconnections in Tympaki and upstream Messara basin using WEAP model

2041	Yield change %	Adaptation Measure	Water consumption Impact	Total impact
Olives	8	deficit Irrigation	-20%	-20%
	20	efficient/smart irrigation systems and scheduling	-18%	
	20	organic farming	-15%	
Grapes	5	deficit Irrigation	-20%	-22%
	20	efficient/smart irrigation systems and scheduling	-21%	
	20	organic farming	-18%	
Vegetables	35	organic farming	-18%	-25%
	35	crops diversification	-21%	
	35	efficient/smart irrigation systems and scheduling	-23%	

Figure 5. Assessment of adaptation measures in agricultures and their effect on the water availability

Figure 6. Current and future dependence on agriculture

Figure 7. Irrigation water status analysis and prediction

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water collection and allocation infrastructure (reservoir-networks) • Good quality of waste water for re-use. • High irrigated area belonging to irrigation communities. • Most of the irrigation channels have minor morphological pressures. • Cost recovery derived from the water use, higher than 80%. • Existence of adequate statistics to monitor the parameters involved in the threats. • Existence of associations concerned and involved in the conservation of water resources. • Local, Regional and National Governments involvement in the conservation and good management of water resources. • Connecting the majority of the population to a water network. 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong seasonality in the annual rainfall volume can lead to complications of supply. • Significant increase in built-up areas. • High surface area occupied by farmland. • Negligible percentage of wastewater reused. • Flood risk caused by episodes of heavy rain. • Loss of aquatic biodiversity due to the presence of biocides, herbicides and pesticides. • Poor state of water transport infrastructure. • High consumption of water for irrigation. • Weak appreciation of associated river spaces. • High degree of erosion in the study area. • Poor quality of riparian vegetation. • Poor Groundwater Quality • Poor groundwater monitoring network
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate legislative framework for proper water management. • Implementation of the measures defined in the Water Framework Directive. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Compliance with environmental objectives. ◦ Promoting active participation of all stakeholders in the implementation of this Directive. ◦ Monitoring of surface water and groundwater. ◦ Cost recovery of water-related services. • Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) associated with good practice for the maintenance of biodiversity, landscape, soil protection and water resources. Specific measures include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Recovery of local varieties with lower water consumption. ◦ Adaptation measures to climate change. ◦ Improving irrigation efficiency. ◦ Ensure compliance with Water Framework Directive. ◦ Avoid use changes and increase agriculture in protected areas. • Rural Development Program <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Ensure the efficient management and sustainable of ecological farming. ◦ Aid for exports of high environmental interest located in Natura 2000. ◦ Subvention of Marginal rainfed crop with constrained profitability, with impact on soil, water, landscape or biodiversity. 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced flows resulting by processes associated with climate change. • Major drought periods during the summer months by processes associated with climate change. • Increased water demand due to rising temperatures associated with climate change. • Increased water temperatures due to rising temperatures from climate change. • Lack of investment in infrastructure due to the economic crisis (wastewater treatment plants, pipelines, saving measures, etc). • Elimination of aid from the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in Europe. • Subvention, by the CMO (Common Market Organization), of crop production highly water consumers or to facilitate the transformation in irrigation (example: olive irrigation in the basin).

Figure 8. SWOT analysis for the Tympaki basin regarding water use and availability

2.1.1. Cost - Benefit Analysis (CBA)

Bayesian decision analysis is usually employed to make decisions in the presence of uncertainty. A common cost-benefit analysis approach coupled with Bayesian decision analysis are applied to aid the decision making of implementing mitigation measures for groundwater resources management. To this end, the full cost-benefit methodology has been established and the optimal options for managed use of groundwater. The mapping of those options is a dynamical process and will be adjusted over the course of the project, where key stakeholders can be added at a different stage to enrich the multi-stakeholder partnership process. The provided information will give insights into assessing the sustainability of the current and future groundwater management strategies. This analysis will identify the impact of the adequate mitigation option considering sustainable water resources availability, management and potential pollution risks.

The decision-making process involves two stages: state estimation and decision making. For state estimation, firstly, all the state parameters θ_i are defined. However, in the Bayesian

approach, a state parameter is an unknown quantity and is considered a random variable that must be determined. The procedure of estimating each θ_i involves previous knowledge on the examined issue and the use of the subjective prior distribution $\pi(\theta_i)$ that expresses the prior information for each state parameter. Next, the Bayesian risk function is obtained to estimate the optimal decision or the decision with the minimum expected risk. The latter also applies in terms of a cost-benefit analysis procedure and denotes the preferable action. The Bayesian decision-making process follows these four steps, while a detailed approach is presented in the flowchart of Figure 9:

Set up the decision-making problem by introducing the possible actions set A and the parametric space θ .

- Action A (0): Use only groundwater
- Action A (1): Surface water – Aquifer recharge

$$L(A(0), Y) = \begin{cases} K_1 Y^2 + GC + LGV, & 0 \leq Y \leq n_1 \\ K_2 Y^2 + GC + LGV, & n_1 < Y \leq n_2 \quad ; \quad K_1 < K_2 < K_3 \\ K_3 Y^2 + GC + LGV, & Y > n_2 \end{cases}$$

where GC denotes the groundwater cost (pumping and volume) and LGV the lost value of groundwater as a sustainable source as soon as it is removed from the aquifer.

Whereas for the action A (1) the following applies,

$$L(A(1), \theta_1) = C + AC + M\theta_1$$

where C is the mitigation measure cost and AC its annual operational cost for the examined auditing period. In case there is a risk (probability) ϑ_1 water needs not to be covered from available water resources of the study area, an additional cost M is applied denoting a supplementary water supply (i.e., water transport) that should be considered. The condition, that shows which action is riskier, is the expression $R=R(A(1))- R(A(0))$.

Establish the expected loss function for each decision $A(i)$, and provide the state of the goal function. If at this step, the parameters θ_i are considered known, then the decision process is

called a cost-benefit analysis, and Step 4 is directly applied. If not, then both Steps 3 and 4 apply.

The goal function is the expected value of the loss function. Thus, for action $A(0)$ the goal function is expressed as follows:

$$G(A(0), \theta_0) = E[L(A(0), Y)] = GC + LCV + \left[K_2 E[Y^2] + K_{1,2} \sum_{Y=0}^{n_1} Y^2 f(Y) + K_{3,2} \sum_{n_2+1}^N Y^2 f(Y) \right]$$

Where $K_{1,2} = K_1 - K_2$ and $K_{3,2} = K_3 - K_2$

$$G(A(1), \theta_1) = E[C + AC + M\theta_1] = C + AC + ME[\theta_1] = C + AC + M\theta_1$$

If θ and θ_1 the state parameters considered known from hydrological information then the cost benefit approach applies by means of Expected Net Loss Present Value (ENLPV).

$$ENLPV = (C + AC + M\theta_1) - L(A(0), \theta_0)$$

Positive ENPLV leads to decision $A(0)$, while negative in decision $A(1)$.

Develop the subjective prior distributions for each θ_i quantifying the previous information.

If Y and Y_1 the state parameters considered unknown then Bayesian analysis is applied in the terms of the Bayesian Risk function that considers prior information in terms of probability density functions to determine Y and Y_1 .

$$R(A(0)) = E^\pi [G(A(0), \theta_0)] = \int_0^1 G(A(0), \theta_0) \pi(\theta) d\theta$$

$$R(A(1)) = E[G(A(1), \theta_1)] = E[C + AC + M\theta_1] = C + AC + ME[\theta_1] = C + AC + M\theta_1$$

Where $\pi(\vartheta)$ denotes the conjugative prior distribution in each case that depends on the fitted probability density function to the data. The probability that over-pumping or a drought year would occur or the necessary surface water would not be available is denoted as a “success” and as a “failure”

The condition, that shows which action is riskier, is the expression

$$R=R(A(1))- R(A(0))$$

Combine Steps 1, 2, and 3 via the risk function. The decision with the minimum expected risk is the optimal decision.

If R is positive, then the decision $A(1)$ is more risky than the decision $A(0)$, and thus, we need to redesign the mitigation measure. On the other hand, for negative values of R , we estimate the volume of ground water needed to cover the water demands. However, the appropriate volume, G , must not exceed the groundwater threshold ($GW_{threshold}$). If Δh is greater than $GW_{threshold}$, then either a water supply demand rebalance is required or an additional water volume WT need to be supplied occasionally in the area as an extra water source to cover the needs. Then, the decision-making process is re-examined to obtain the least-cost approach.

Figure 9. Flowchart of Bayesian Risk and cost-benefit risk analysis

Considering the available information for Tympaki basin and applying the proposed methodology it is obtained that for up to 15 overpumping violations using scaled cost effects, action $A(0)$ is more affordable compared to action $A(1)$ (groundwater only) involving aquifer recharge of 0.9 Mm^3 (**18%**) plus 2 Mm^3 (**40%**) from the reservoir to cover the needs, 1.1 Mm^3 (**22%**) groundwater and 1 Mm^3 (**20%**) waste water treatment plant effluent for irrigation. For more violations the financial and environmental costs of the mitigation measure: aquifer recharge and surface water use are lower compared to groundwater use only. According to the decision-making flowchart an assessment follows for the impact of the groundwater level decline in the aquifer considering the withdraw amount to cover the demand. The study area A and the storativity coefficient S are considered. Therefore, the expected aquifer level decline was calculated, $\Delta h = G / (A \times S_y)$, equal to 0.38 m/yr , less than 2.0 m/yr that may affect the set aquifer level threshold which is 10 meters above sea level according to the coastal area average. Therefore, considering the sustainable water resources policy that the local authorities desire to follow and the history of aquifer overpumping in the area, the investment to an integrated aquifer recharge scheme with balanced use of the available water resources of the basin is suggested. A similar and more detailed approach incorporating more information will be applied in the next steps of the project according to the climate change scenarios.

2.2. Environmental Criteria

2.2.1. Groundwater Quantity

The simulation – optimization procedure consists of 3 components/sub-routines:

1. The groundwater modelling
2. The construction of a response matrix based on iterative simulation runs of the groundwater model.
3. The optimization of the pumping rates by using the response matrix and applying a piece-wise linear optimizations approach. The objective of the optimization is to control the saltwater intrusion, which is the main pollution problem of the groundwater body.

2.2.1.1. Groundwater Modelling with FEFLOW

The study area has a width of about 12.5 km and a length of about 9.1 km. There are 371 pumping wells which were grouped into 20 by using the K-nearest neighbors and each group was represented as one pumping well by using the Median Center method, which Identifies the location that minimizes overall Euclidean distance to the features in a dataset (Figure 10). The pumping rate of each group is the total pumping rate of all the wells constituting the group in m³/d. The pumping rates are imported in FEFLOW as timeseries with the values being different for the wet and dry season.

Figure 10. Tympaki study site with all the wells along with the representative ones for each group

The discretization of the unconfined aquifer was applied using a triangular finite element mesh which consists of 11877 nodes and 15340 elements. There are 2 layers and each one of them has 7670 elements and 3 slices with 3959 nodes for each slice. The depth of the model comprises 130 m deep from the sea level for the unconfined aquifer. The data for the hydraulic conductivity were extracted from the Decentralized Administration of Crete and they were set for the axis $x'x$ and $y'y$. For $z'z$ the hydraulic conductivity was 10% of the value of $x'x$. The pumping wells as considered in the model are depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Pumping wells as introduced in the FEFLOW model

The calibration – validation process was conducted as follows: In the area of Tympaki, there are 6 observation wells that are scattered in the study area, as shown in Figure 12. The hydraulic head data are used as timeseries and the period for each well is different. The timeseries period for the precipitation, observation wells and pumping wells are available for the years 2004-2014. For the precipitation, the data of one station is used. In sake of computational time, a mean precipitation was used with a step of 10 days and the input timeseries is in units of m/d. The data from 04/2004 until 04/2009 are used for calibration and the rest of the period are used for validation. During the validation period, the field measurements at the observation wells were conducted in random dates so there are periods with no data available in the observation wells. However, the validation results are based on these scarce in situ data and they mean absolute error for each observation well is presented in the following Table 4.

Table 4. Mean absolute error at the observation wells – validation results

Observation well	Mean Absolute error (m)
“M1”	9.66
“M2”	9.04
“NH14”	6.28
“C46”	4.48
“Aerodromio”	2.56
“A3”	6.84

Figure 12. Observation wells with calibration – validation data available

For the model of the Tympaki area, a first-type flow boundary condition was used along the coastline, where the hydraulic head was set at 0 m (msl). Also, a second-type boundary conditions were set at the north boundaries of the study area. Those boundary conditions are connected to the precipitation so there is a fluctuation to the hydraulic head that is relative to the rainfall. The observation wells that are used in the pumping scenarios were set to monitor

the saltwater intrusion zone. As it appears in Figure 13, the saltwater intrusion zone is calculated at 3.25 meters above the sea level (at the end of the calibration period), by using the Ghyben – Herzberg relation and considering the depth of the deepest pumping well in the area (226 m below the sea level). The simulation runs are applied for a ten-year period from 01/04/2010 until 31/03/2020, using the available precipitation data, as well as timeseries for the pumping rates. For the values of pumping rates obtained from the licences of water use, the results of the model are depicted in Figures 14 and 15 and the values of the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 16.

Figure 13. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of calibration period

Figure 14. Current situation at the end of the wet period of the 10-year simulation

Figure 15. Current situation at the end of the dry period of the 10-year simulation

Figure 16. Hydraulic heads at the observation wells according to the current situation

2.2.1.2. Creation of the Response Matrix

The response matrix is created by sequentially disturbing the initial pumping rates of the m pumping wells, then running the simulation model and obtaining the hydraulic heads at n observation wells. The response matrix A is the $n \times m$ matrix, with its elements consisting of the values of hydraulic head's response to the disturbance of the pumping rate: $\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q}$.

2.2.1.3. Optimization of Pumping Rates

The optimization problem is set as:

$$\max Q$$

s. t.:

- $H \geq H_{ref}$
- $\sum Q = \text{Groundwater Demand}$

Where: $H = H_o + \partial H$ and $\partial H = A * \partial Q$

Therefore, the constraint:

$$H_o + \partial H \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * \partial Q \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * (Q - Q_o) \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$A * Q \geq H_{ref} - H_o + A * Q_o$$

The problem is transformed to be in line with the requirements of Matlab optimization tool as:

$$\min(-Q)$$

$$s. t. : -A * Q \leq H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$$

$-A$, the constraint coefficients matrix and

$b = H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$, the vector of constraints of the linear problem.

H_{ref} is the target value for the groundwater level that is set by the decision maker. In this report, different values for H_{ref} were considered for the execution of the optimization runs. In the report for Deliverable D6.2, the value for H_{ref} is set to be about 6m. This means that the optimization procedure gives as result the pumping rates that should be used to keep the groundwater level up to 6m high. When considering the current pumping rates, the groundwater level at the observations points was found to be about 5m. Therefore, the value of 6m was defined in order to raise the groundwater level 1m above the level that occurs when applying the current pumping rates. When groundwater level is raised, the saltwater intrusion front is attenuated. Saltwater intrusion contributes to the degradation of the qualitative characteristics of water; irrigation with saline water may lead to lower crop yield and soil degradation. Even though there are limits for the qualitative characteristics to assess the suitability of water for irrigation purposes, there are no limits for saltwater intrusion, since it is dependent on the hydrogeology of each area. Specifically, for the Tympaki study area, the Water Directorate has set the water abstraction permits so as to control overexploitation. Based on the hydraulic control, this could limit the saltwater intrusion.

Groundwater Demand is determined by the results of the Cost-Benefit Analysis that was presented in the previous section. The water resources distribution is determined through the CBA and the groundwater use that is calculated serves as the input for groundwater optimization.

Although the problem is not linear, it is solved by using the Simplex method in the frame of the piece-wise linear technique. Thus, after the first simulation – optimization cycle, the results for the optimum pumping rates are used in order to run again the simulation procedure, create the response matrix and apply the optimization procedure. The cycle is repeated until the results of two consecutive cycles converge to the same values for the individual wells and the total pumping rates as well. The results of the Tympaki study area are presented in the next section.

2.2.2. Results of the Simulation - Optimization Algorithm

At first, the simulation model was run for zero pumping rates. The saltwater intrusion zone is depicted in Figures 17 and 18, while the hydraulic heads at the observation wells in Figure 19. Then, the disturbance was set to 800 m³/day for one well at a time and the model was run separately for each disturbance in the corresponding pumping well. The results of the model for the hydraulic heads in the observation wells are in the 350th simulation step for the end of the dry period and in the 365th simulation step for the wet one. These results are recorded in Tables 5 and 6 for each simulation run and respective disturbance in the pumping wells. In this set of runs, the first response matrix *A* was retrieved as follows in Table 7 for the Dry Season and in Table 8 for the Wet Season.

Figure 17. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the dry period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 18. Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the wet period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 19. Hydraulic head in the observation wells considering zero pumping rates

Table 5. Results of the simulation model - Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the dry season when considering zero pumping rates

Simul. Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation Well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	8.062363	8.515735	8.09704	8.500163	8.246379	8.492439	8.136183	8.490928	8.247511	8.327616	8.392923
R1	8.028379	8.470545	8.063345	8.45532	8.215493	8.448152	8.100444	8.447421	8.210038	8.287694	8.351131
R2	8.025531	8.476084	8.059861	8.460445	8.203752	8.450493	8.096794	8.447096	8.20567	8.281288	8.346124
R3	8.034139	8.459457	8.069227	8.444508	8.227885	8.43866	8.105735	8.44021	8.215087	8.289915	8.349379
R4	8.050494	8.507137	8.084746	8.4917	8.231376	8.482782	8.122806	8.480166	8.232749	8.311556	8.379094
R5	8.029436	8.466444	8.064596	8.451501	8.221748	8.44482	8.101194	8.444665	8.210867	8.287461	8.349762
R6	8.048526	8.453117	8.082819	8.442191	8.230791	8.447671	8.121219	8.454485	8.231178	8.307245	8.3669
R7	8.026039	8.471146	8.061229	8.455801	8.217177	8.448094	8.098081	8.446973	8.20811	8.286104	8.35007
R8	8.037851	8.509672	8.072611	8.49435	8.225151	8.48591	8.116352	8.483896	8.230663	8.316098	8.384129
R9	8.034556	8.455279	8.069661	8.44194	8.22469	8.438912	8.106259	8.441619	8.215785	8.291066	8.351004
R10	8.008265	8.484565	8.042866	8.469055	8.192627	8.4596	8.082998	8.456449	8.195878	8.283065	8.354017
R11	7.98478	8.497638	8.014678	8.481674	8.162338	8.472528	8.06684	8.469537	8.195908	8.293935	8.366803
R12	8.035878	8.498156	8.070279	8.482597	8.218075	8.472811	8.105415	8.469048	8.212077	8.288769	8.363705
R13	8.026825	8.471462	8.061786	8.456063	8.212435	8.448546	8.098983	8.447556	8.209042	8.287046	8.350911
R14	8.024205	8.472842	8.058551	8.457806	8.214351	8.449282	8.09624	8.447444	8.206124	8.284437	8.349258
R15	8.045973	8.480261	8.081069	8.462491	8.228095	8.448141	8.117967	8.442773	8.227444	8.301043	8.356462
R16	8.042262	8.506376	8.076554	8.491107	8.234863	8.48227	8.114219	8.479866	8.225028	8.308772	8.378465
R17	8.049289	8.512084	8.084343	8.496338	8.232813	8.488302	8.124327	8.486537	8.237051	8.320172	8.38725
R18	8.054364	8.481212	8.089056	8.468851	8.24757	8.467113	8.12756	8.469849	8.23803	8.315737	8.37769
R19	8.017876	8.477733	8.052768	8.461985	8.199913	8.453336	8.091242	8.451046	8.202478	8.284152	8.351302
R20	8.049884	8.501994	8.084652	8.486351	8.241845	8.476638	8.122024	8.473316	8.231538	8.307011	8.371512

Table 6. Results of the simulation model - Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the wet season when considering zero pumping rates

Simul. Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation Well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	14.949	15.18338	14.81602	15.11287	15.03934	15.13988	14.78852	15.10108	14.85455	14.87993	14.94165
R1	14.91422	15.13834	14.78079	15.06821	14.99795	15.09553	14.75209	15.05722	14.81706	14.83994	14.89983
R2	14.91237	15.14419	14.77946	15.07277	15.004	15.09795	14.74903	15.05718	14.81273	14.83363	14.89485
R3	14.92063	15.12714	14.78701	15.05722	14.9978	15.0861	14.75808	15.05014	14.82211	14.8422	14.8981
R4	14.93728	15.17524	14.80446	15.10404	15.02874	15.13024	14.77499	15.09023	14.83981	14.86389	14.92781
R5	14.91597	15.13415	14.78233	15.0642	14.9945	15.09226	14.75359	15.05461	14.8179	14.83975	14.89849
R6	14.93528	15.12143	14.80254	15.05468	15.02546	15.09511	14.77336	15.06454	14.83823	14.85958	14.91562
R7	14.91259	15.1387	14.779	15.06842	14.99244	15.09554	14.75051	15.05693	14.81514	14.8384	14.8988
R8	14.92459	15.17762	14.79226	15.10662	15.01751	15.13337	14.76847	15.09394	14.83771	14.86843	14.93285
R9	14.92113	15.123	14.78752	15.05461	15.00204	15.08635	14.7587	15.05159	14.82282	14.84337	14.89973
R10	14.89498	15.15281	14.76242	15.0815	14.98311	15.10705	14.73511	15.06648	14.80293	14.83539	14.90274
R11	14.87139	15.16506	14.73292	15.09426	14.93769	15.11997	14.71957	15.07952	14.80293	14.84624	14.91553
R12	14.92258	15.16659	14.7892	15.09503	15.00917	15.12026	14.7572	15.07907	14.81912	14.84108	14.91243
R13	14.9134	15.13881	14.78004	15.06871	14.99904	15.09599	14.75137	15.05754	14.81609	14.83938	14.89963
R14	14.91089	15.14127	14.77811	15.07017	14.99135	15.09673	14.7485	15.05746	14.81317	14.83675	14.89798
R15	14.9326	15.14766	14.79898	15.0752	15.02237	15.09559	14.77031	15.053	14.83449	14.85334	14.90517
R16	14.92894	15.17472	14.79591	15.10343	15.00827	15.12974	14.76636	15.08968	14.83207	14.86109	14.9272
R17	14.93591	15.17957	14.80268	15.10907	15.02832	15.13574	14.77676	15.09643	14.84409	14.87249	14.93598
R18	14.94105	15.14948	14.80796	15.08117	15.02112	15.11454	14.77968	15.07992	14.84507	14.86805	14.92642
R19	14.9045	15.1453	14.7715	15.07471	14.99448	15.10079	14.74365	15.06109	14.80952	14.83647	14.90002
R20	14.93656	15.17018	14.80324	15.09868	15.01677	15.12408	14.7742	15.0832	14.83858	14.85933	14.92024

Table 7. Response matrix for the dry season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.9	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.0	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Table 8. Response matrix for the wet season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.8	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.0	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

The optimum pumping rates were determined for four different values for the water table level of reference, H_{ref} : a) $H_{ref} = 6,25$ m (upgrading water level up to 0,60 m), b) $H_{ref} = 6,5$ m (upgrading water level up to 0,85 m), c) $H_{ref} = 6,75$ m (upgrading water level up to 1,1 m) and d) $H_{ref} = 7$ m (upgrading water level up to 1,35 m). The water table level in the observation wells is constrained to values greater than H_{ref} . Additionally, the lower bounds of the pumping rates were set to zero and the upper bounds were determined by the licenses held.

2.2.2.1. Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref}=6,25$ m

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6,25$ m were found after 2 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 7 and 8). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as recorded in Table 9.

Table 9. b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.8124	1	8.699
2	2.2657	2	8.9334
3	1.8470	3	8.5660
4	2.2502	4	8.8629
5	1.9964	5	8.7893
6	2.2424	6	8.8899
7	1.8862	7	8.5385
8	2.2409	8	8.8511
9	1.9975	9	8.6046
10	2.0776	10	8.6299
11	2.1429	11	8.6917

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 10 for the wet and the dry season.

Table 10. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.25$ m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82

Table 10. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of Href=6.25m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
8	474.19	381.20
9	1497.99	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1559.42	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 10% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 11. The second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix.

Table 11. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of Href=6.25m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1497.99	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1559.42	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04

Table 11. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of Href=6.25m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

The values obtained from the second iteration are the same with these of the first one. Therefore, these pumping rates are the optimum ones for upgrading the water table level up to 0,60 m and for the dry season are graphically presented in Figure 20. The saltwater intrusion zone is shown in Figures 21 and 22 and the water level in the observation wells in Figure 23.

Figure 20. Optimum pumping rates for the dry season

Figure 21. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$

Figure 22. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$

Figure 23. Hydraulic heads in the observation wells considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.25m$

2.2.2.2. Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref}=6,5 m$

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6,5m$ were found after 3 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 7 and 8). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as shown in Table 12.

Table 12. b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.562363	1	8.449
2	2.015735	2	8.68338
3	1.59704	3	8.31602
4	2.000163	4	8.61287
5	1.746379	5	8.53934
6	1.992439	6	8.63988
7	1.636183	7	8.28852
8	1.990928	8	8.60108
9	1.747511	9	8.35455
10	1.827616	10	8.37993
11	1.892923	11	8.44165

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 13 for the wet and the dry season.

Table 13. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.5m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1371.23	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1280.68	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7080·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 10% of the initial pumping rate. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 14. The simulation results, the second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix.

Table 14. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of Href=6.5m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1498.00	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1472.43	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7399·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

Concerning the wet season, the optimum values from the two consecutive runs are the same. However, for the dry season, there are two pumping wells that their pumping rates have a difference in their values, as shown in Figure 24. Therefore, the same procedure is repeated for a third time and optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 15. For the third set of runs, the disturbance was set to 20% of the initial pumping rate. The simulation results, the third response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix. The optimum values of the third iteration converge with these from the second one, as depicted in Figure 25. Therefore, the problem has been linearized and the final optimum values are those of the third iteration.

Table 15. Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the third run of Href=6.5m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1498.00	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1464.07	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7390·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

Figure 24. Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first and second S-O runs for $H_{ref}=6.5m$

Figure 25. Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first, second and third S-O runs for $H_{ref}=6.5m$

The hydraulic head level in the observation wells is shown in the following Figure 28 and the saltwater intrusion front at the end of the dry and the wet period of the 10-year simulation in Figures 26 and 27.

Figure 26. Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$

Figure 27.: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$

Figure 28. Hydraulic heads in observation wells when considering optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6.5m$

2.2.2.3. Simulation and Optimization – Situation for the Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref}=6.75$ m

The simulation – optimization runs that were executed aiming at upgrading the water table level up to 1.1 m followed the pattern summarized in Table 16.

2.2.2.4. Simulation and Optimization – Situation for the Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref}= 7$ m

The simulation – optimization runs that were executed aiming at upgrading the water table level up to 1.35 m followed the pattern summarized in Table 17.

Table 16. Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for Href=6.75m

Run	Initial Pumping Rates	Disturbances		Optimum Values for Pumping Rates	Number of Wells in which there is convergence with previous run's results	Total Pumping Rates (m ³ /day)	
		If Q ₀ = 0	If Q ₀ ≠ 0			Dry Season	Wet Season
1	0	800	0.1 of Q ₀	Qopt1	-	3.2451 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
2	Qopt1	800	0.1 of Q ₀	Qopt2	13	3.7331 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
3	Qopt2	800	0.2 of Q ₀	Qopt3	14	3.7357 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
4	Qopt3	800	0.3 of Q ₀	Qopt4	13	3.2931 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
5	Qopt4	800	0.4 of Q ₀	Qopt5	13	3.2860 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
6	Qopt5	800	0.5 of Q ₀	Qopt6	12	3.3457 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
7	Qopt6	800	0.6 of Q ₀	Qopt7	14	3.3008 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
8	Qopt7	800	0.7 of Q ₀	Qopt8	18	3.7486 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
9a	Qopt8	800	0.8 of Q ₀	Qopt9a	14	3.2886 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
9b	Qopt8	800	0.1 of Q ₀	Qopt9b	17	3.2881 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴
11	Qopt9b	800	0.2 of Q ₀	Qopt11	13	3.3189 · 10 ⁴	3.1254 · 10 ⁴

Table 17. Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for $H_{ref}=7$ m

Run	Initial Pumping Rates	Disturbances		Optimum Values for Pumping Rates	Number of Wells in which there is convergence with previous run's results	Total Pumping Rates (m^3/day)	
		If $Q_0 = 0$	If $Q_0 \neq 0$			Dry Season	Wet Season
1	0	800	0.1 of Q_0	Q_{opt1}	-	$2.7644 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
2	Q_{opt1}	800	0.1 of Q_0	Q_{opt2}	11	$2.8303 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
3	Q_{opt2}	800	0.2 of Q_0	Q_{opt3}	12	$3.5512 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
4	Q_{opt3}	800	0.3 of Q_0	Q_{opt4}	13	$2.7824 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
5	Q_{opt4}	800	0.4 of Q_0	Q_{opt5}	15	$2.8229 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
6a	Q_{opt5}	800	0.5 of Q_0	Q_{opt6a}	12	$2.8425 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
6b	Q_{opt5}	800	0.1 of Q_0	Q_{opt6b}	13	$3.3961 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

2.2.2.5. Discussion

The piece-wise linear technique was applied for four different values of the hydraulic head of reference (scenarios) and for the same 10-year period of simulation, with precipitation data available. As observed from the different scenarios, the higher the hydraulic head of reference, the more difficult to obtain the optimum values of the pumping rates. For the two first scenarios, the optimum values were found after two and three iterations, respectively. On the other hand, in the third and fourth scenarios, an optimal solution could not be found at all. In these scenarios, it was also observed that after a certain number of iterations, a maximum number of wells in which there is convergence between two consecutive runs exists, but does not reach the total number of the pumping wells. Therefore, it is assumed that the constraint is strict enough so as not to enable the finding of the optimum solution for the certain duration of the simulation period.

As the research progresses, new scenarios will be formed in order to find the optimum pumping rates for different hydraulic heads of reference, but in longer simulation periods. In addition, for the next steps, it is planned to perform the training of the Fuzzy Inference System that will combine the different optimization criteria (social, economic and environmental) in order to obtain the optimum solution based on these multiple criteria.

3. Environmental Data Management System

An environmental data management system has been created in order to gather and mine the environmental data. The design of the database includes the storage of the collected data in a coherent environmental database management system (DBMS) for further use within the project. A critical issue that was taken into is the existence of queries for automatic updating, importing data, exporting data, selecting specific subsets and grouping records. The database was connected with an open-source business intelligence tool, which helps users question the database and visualize answers in useful optical formats that can be shared.

3.1. Type of Database

The two most common types of databases are the relational and Not only SQL databases (NoSQL). The relational model, introduced by Edgar F. Codd in the early 1970's, defines a methodology for organizing structured data into relations (tables with columns and rows) and for defining the relationships between those tables. Each table contains a primary key and must be indexed. A primary key is a field which is guaranteed to have a unique entry for each record in a table. Indexes provide a quick navigation through the database, in order to retrieve specific data subsets. The entries in the attribute chosen as index should be unique or rare, within that field. Usually, the primary key will be chosen as an index, although this is not a requirement. Relational databases can be normalised to improve performance of queries, reduce data duplication and make the database more elegant.

At the heart of the relational model is the Structured Query Language (SQL), a standards-based programming language used to define database schema and the relationships between tables. The language is also used to store, manipulate, and retrieve data from those tables. SQL has been adopted by both the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and is well known and widely supported by developers around the globe.

Relational databases offer many important features that make them aptly suited to enterprise workloads, which is why organizations have been turning to them for so long. They're optimized for handling highly structured data, and their inherent characteristics—such as normalization, atomicity, and consistency—ensure the integrity of that data throughout its lifespan. These features also contribute to better storage utilization, while providing flexible

query support through standards-based SQL. However, relational databases are not appropriate for semi-structured or unstructured data, especially at scale. A relational database also requires a rigid schema that must be carefully planned and does not easily accommodate changing requirements, leaving little room for the dynamic nature of many of today's applications and development methodologies.

Due to the existence of highly structured data in the current project, the database schema is predefined, resulting in a rigid structure that helps to optimize storage and ensure data integrity. Furthermore, there is a crucial need for performing complex queries against the structured data. Finally, a high degree of data integrity, adhering to the principles of atomicity, consistency, isolation, and durability is also necessary, along with a mature database technology, that is supported by large developer communities. Thus, a relational database best suits the needs of the current project.

3.2. Relational Database Management System

MySQL is a popular, high performance, open-source, relational DBMS (Database Management System), paired with ongoing development and support from Oracle. MySQL can be used in conjunction with MySQL Workbench, a unified visual tool which provides data modelling, SQL development and comprehensive administration tools for server configuration, user administration, backup, and much more. It is platform agnostic and makes interactions with relational databases much easier. Often associated with internet applications or web services, MySQL was designed to be extensively compatible with other technologies and architectures. The RDBMS runs on all major computing platforms, including Unix-based operating systems, such as the myriad Linux distributions or Mac OS and Windows. MySQL's client-server architecture means it can support a variety of backends, as well as different programming interfaces. Third-party migration tools further allow MySQL to move data to and from a vast set of general storage systems, whether these are designed to be on-premises or cloud-based. MySQL can be deployed in virtualized environments, distributed or centralized, and even exists as portable standalone libraries for learning purposes, testing, or small applications. MySQL's wide compatibility with all these other systems and software makes it a particularly practical choice of RDBMS in most situations. Any individual or enterprise may freely use, modify, publish, and expand on Oracle's open-source MySQL code base. The software is released under

the GNU General Public License (GPL). The public and community-based nature of open-source releases enriches MySQL's documentation and online support culture, while also ensuring that sustained or newly-developed capabilities never stray too far from current user needs.

Due to the features described above, MySQL is perfectly suited for the environmental data within this project, so it will be used for all interactions throughout it.

3.3. Design Features

Normalization is a database design technique that reduces data redundancy and eliminates undesirable characteristics like insertion, update and deletion anomalies. Normalization rules divide larger tables into smaller and link them using relationships. Thus, Normal Forms are used to eliminate or reduce redundancy in database tables. There are different levels of normalisation, such as:

- **1st Normal Form (1NF)**

If a relation contains composite or multi-valued attribute, it violates first Normal Form or a relation is in first Normal Form if it does not contain any composite or multi-valued attribute. Thus, repeated sets of related data are removed and put into an individual table, where each set of related data has its own separate table and is identified with a primary key.

- **2nd Normal Form (2NF)**

To be in second Normal Form, a relation must be in first normal form and relation must not contain any partial dependency. A relation is in 2NF if it has no partial dependency, i.e., no non-prime attribute (attributes which are not part of any candidate key) is dependent on any proper subset of any candidate key of the table.

- **3rd Normal Form (3NF)**

A table is considered in third Normal Form if the table/entity is already in the second Normal Form and the columns of the table/entity are non-transitively dependent on the primary key.

- **Boyce-Codd Normal Form (BCNF)**

A relation is in Boyce-Codd Normal Form (BCNF) if every determinant is a candidate key. The difference between 3NF and BCNF is that for a functional dependency $A \rightarrow B$, 3NF allows this

dependency in a relation if B is a primary-key attribute and A is not a candidate key, whereas BCNF insists that for this dependency to remain in a relation, A must be a candidate key.

In the context of the current project, every table was designed by means of describing one characteristic (i.e., weather station, temperature measurement, rain measurement) and the associated data which is necessary for describing that characteristic. 3NF normalization was used in order to eliminate or reduce redundancy in database tables and to improve the performance of queries. Thus, every table present on the database satisfies the criteria of 2NF, non-primary key columns shouldn't depend on other non-primary key columns and there is absence of transitive functional dependencies.

3.4. Metabase: a Brief Overview

Metabase is a rapidly growing open-source business intelligence tool, crafted in such a way that all kinds of charts, plots and graphs with different designs can be positioned simultaneously for data visualization. Moreover, Metabase's intuitive interface lets you ask questions on your data and displays answers in famous downloadable formats. Questions can be saved, making it easy to come back to them and they can also be grouped into dashboards in order to be shared with the rest of your team. Metabase uses the MariaDB connector to connect easily to MariaDB and MySQL servers. It sets up really quickly, connecting to your database and bringing its data to life in beautiful visualizations, opening data up for everyone, not just analysts and developers

Metabase home page allows some automatic explorations of the tables that a user can look at and save as a dashboard, an area where things that the teammates create will show up, along with a link to explore all the created dashboards and saved questions. Once some dashboards have been created, any of them that are pinned in the main "Our analytics" collection will show up on the homepage for all of the teammates.

3.4.1. Browsing Data

If a connection is finally established between Metabase and a database, the current database is listed at the bottom of the homepage along with the sample dataset that Metabase comes with. Users can easily click on a database to see its contents and can easily click on a table to see its rows. Moreover, by clicking on the bolt icon to x-ray a table, the user can see an

automatic exploration of it. Metabase can present the data in a variety of ways, just by changing the visualization mode from the “Visualization” sidebar.

IdTemp	TempDate	TempM	TempH	TempHTime	TempL	TempLTime	Station IdStation
1	November 1, 2009	15.4	17	12:50 AM	13.5	6:50 PM	1
2	November 2, 2009	14.3	15.6	1:50 PM	12.4	2:50 AM	1
3	November 3, 2009	17.1	21.6	11:20 PM	11.5	3:00 AM	1
4	November 4, 2009	18.8	21.1	1:10 PM	15.3	9:00 AM	1
5	November 5, 2009	18.5	22.5	3:30 PM	13.9	5:40 AM	1
6	November 6, 2009	20.6	22.1	12:40 PM	16.7	12:40 AM	1
7	November 7, 2009	20.9	22.2	1:40 PM	20.1	7:00 AM	1
8	November 8, 2009	19.7	21.7	7:00 AM	16.8	10:10 AM	1
9	November 9, 2009	18.6	22.2	1:00 PM	14.6	7:00 AM	1
10	November 10, 2009	20.8	23.2	10:50 AM	15.7	12:30 AM	1
11	November 11, 2009	20.2	22.2	12:40 AM	17.7	7:30 AM	1

Figure 29. Sample visualization of temperature data as a table

Figure 30. Sample visualization of temperature data as a scatter-plot

3.4.2. Asking Questions

Metabase’s two core concepts are questions and their corresponding answers. Everything else is based around questions and answers. A user can ask a question in Metabase by clicking the “Ask a Question” button at the top of the screen. There are three ways to ask a specific question in Metabase:

- The simple question mode, which lets the user filter, summarize and visualize data.
- The custom question mode, which gives the user a powerful notebook-style editor to create more complex questions that require joins, multiple stages of filtering and aggregating, or custom columns.
- The SQL/native query editor.

The answers can be downloaded as an .xlsx, .csv, or .json file. The maximum download size is 1 million rows.

3.4.2.1. Simple Questions

After the user selects the Simple Question option, he will need to pick some data that has a question about. The Simple Question could be on a user's table or something like events, orders or downloads. Moreover, there are options for filtering data and/or summarizing them. By clicking the "Filter" option, a list of all of the columns in the browsed table, as well as columns from tables that are related to the current table, appears. Depending on the column picked, there are slightly different options for the filter. Generally, there are three types of columns, each with their own set of filtering options:

- Numeric columns let the user add filters to only include table rows where the values of the attribute are between two specific values, greater or less than a specific value or exactly equal to a specific value.
- With text or category columns, users can specify that only want to include data where this column is or isn't a specific option or can exclude rows that don't have a value for this column.
- Date columns give a calendar or input box so that specific time ranges or all days before or after a certain date can be selected.

Metabase administrators own the option to create special named filters for the tables and if they do so, the filters appear at the top of the filter dropdown in purple text with a star next to them. These are called "segments" and they are shortcuts to a combination of filters that are commonly used by the members of the team sharing the database.

The “Summarize” option has two main parts. The metric desired and the type of data group. By default, the “count of rows” metric will be selected, since it’s super common, but it can easily be changed. The user can also select more than one metric to view. The available metrics are listed below:

- Count of rows: the total of number of rows in the table, after any filters have been applied.
- Sum of: the sum of all the values in a specific column.
- Average of: the average of all the values in a single column.
- Number of distinct values of: the number of unique values in all the cells of a single column.
- Cumulative sum of: a running total for a specific column. In order for this metric to be useful the user needs to group it by a date column to see it across time.
- Cumulative count of rows: a running total of the number of rows in the table over time. Just like “Cumulative sum of”, the user needs to group this by a date column in order for it to be useful.
- Standard deviation of: a number which expresses how much the values of a column vary, plus or minus, from the average value of that column.
- Minimum of: the minimum value present in the selected field.
- Maximum of: the maximum value present in the selected field.

Figure 31. Sample of summarizing data in a simple question

3.4.2.2. Custom Questions with Notebook Editor

If the user has a question that’s a bit more involved than a simple question, he can create a custom question using the notebook editor, by clicking the “Ask a Question” button in the top navigation bar and selecting “Custom Question”.

The notebook is made up of a sequence of individual steps. Under each step, there are buttons to add more steps after the current one. To the right of each step is a preview button that shows the first 10 rows of the results of the question up to that step.

This first step is required and is where the user picks the data that wants to base the question on. In most cases, users pick one of the tables in the database created, but they can also choose a previously saved question’s result as the starting point for the new question. What this means in practice is that the user can do things like use complex SQL queries to create new tables that can be used as starting data in a question just like any other table in your database.

The users can have most saved questions as source data, provided they have permission to view that question. They can even use questions that were saved as a chart rather than a table. Although, there are some kinds of saved questions that can’t be used as source data:

- Druid questions,
- Google Analytics questions,
- Mongo questions,

- questions that use “Cumulative Sum” or “Cumulative Count” aggregations,
- questions that have columns that are named the same or similar thing, like “Count” and “Count 2”.

During the next step of custom question design, the user has the option to select one or more columns to filter on. Adding a summarize step lets the user choose how to aggregate the data from the previous step. He can pick one or more metrics and optionally group those metrics by one or more columns. When picking the metrics, the user can choose from basic functions like sum, average and count, can pick a common metric that an admin has defined or can create a custom expression by writing a formula.

Furthermore, the user can join data to combine current table with others or even with a saved question. Currently joins are not available, if the starting data is from a Google Analytics or MongoDB database. After clicking on the ‘Join Data’ button to add a join step, the user needs to pick the data that he wants to join. It’s important, that he can only pick tables and saved questions that are from the same database as your starting data. Next, the user needs to pick the columns he wants to join on. This means that he must pick a column from the first table and a column from the second table and the join will stitch rows together where the value from the first column is equal to the value in the second column. A very common example is to join on an ID column in each table, so if happened to pick a table to join on where there is a foreign key relationship between the tables, Metabase will automatically pick those corresponding ID columns. At the end of join step, there’s a ‘Columns’ button that the user can click to choose which columns he wants to include from the joined data. By default, Metabase will do a left outer join, but there is a Venn diagram icon to select a different type of join. Metabase supports multiple stages of joins and joins on multiple conditions. Not all databases support all types of joins, so Metabase will only display the options supported by the database you’re using.

Here are the basic types of joins:

- Left outer join: select all records from Table A, along with records from Table B that meet the join condition, if any.

- Right outer join: select all records from Table B, along with records from Table A that meet the join condition, if any.
- Inner join: only select the records from Table A and B where the join condition is met.
- Full outer join: select all records from both tables, whether or not the join condition is met.

Figure 32. Sample of implementing a custom question (joining and filtering), through Notebook Editor

3.4.2.3 Advanced Questions in Native Query Editor

If a user has the permissions to use the Native Query Editor, he can directly write SQL or his database's native querying language. If any user writes a SQL query that includes variables, the question might have filter widgets at the top of the screen. Filter widgets let the user modify the SQL query before its run, changing the final results. Any team member can use SQL snippets to save, reuse and share SQL code across multiple questions that are composed using the SQL editor.

Figure 33. Sample of implementing an advanced question in Native Query Editor

3.4.3. Dashboards, Collections, Pulses

Dashboards group questions and present them on a single page. Dashboards are shareable reports that feature a set of related questions. Subscriptions to dashboards can be set via email or Slack to receive the exported results of the dashboard’s questions. A dashboard comprises a set of cards arranged on a grid. These cards can be questions, such as tables, charts, maps or text boxes. Users can add filter widgets to dashboards that filter data identically across multiple questions and customize what happens when their teammates click on a chart or a table. In Metabase parlance, every chart on a dashboard is called a “question.” Clicking on the title of a question on a dashboard will take the user to a detail view of that question. When you’re looking at the detail view of a question, you can use all the same actions mentioned above. You can also click on the headings of tables to see more options, like summing the values of a column, or filtering based on that column. If the Metabase administrator has enabled public sharing on a dashboard, the user can go to that dashboard and click on the sharing icon to find its public links. Public links can be viewed by anyone, even if they don’t have access to Metabase. The public embedding code can be used to embed the dashboard in a simple web page or a blog post.

Collections in Metabase are a lot like folders. They’re where all team’s dashboards and charts are kept. In order to explore a collection, a user must just click on one in the “Our analytics” section of the home page or click on “Browse all items”.

The Pulses feature in Metabase gives users the ability to automatically send regular updates to their teammates to help everyone keep track of changes to the metrics that matter them most. Because of the space constraints of email and Slack, Metabase will automatically make some adjustments to the appearance of the saved question so that it looks great in the Pulse. For

example, in order to save space, pie charts will automatically be transformed into bar charts. Users can also optionally include the results of a saved question in an emailed pulse as a .csv or .xls file attachment. Users can also set a different delivery schedule for email versus Slack. To deliver by email, the users have to type in the Metabase user names, or email addresses they want to send the pulse to, separated by commas. Then, they have to choose to either send it daily, weekly, or monthly and the time at which they want it to be sent. To send via Slack, the users need to choose which channel they want to post the pulse in, whether they want it to post hourly or daily and at what time. Again, the schedule for Slack can be different from the schedule for email.

The search bar is a quick way to find dashboards, questions, collections and pulses. The user can select from the typeahead’s dropdown results or hit enter to view a search results page.

Figure 34. Sample dashboard

Appendix

The Appendix contains the tables for the response matrices, the constraints vectors and the results of the piece-wise linear optimization for the different selected values of the hydraulic head of reference. For the hydraulic heads of reference equal to 6.75 m and 7 m are provided only the results of the pumping rates through the different iterations in order to justify that an optimal solution could not be found.

For $H_{ref}=6,25$ m
Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.9	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.0	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.8	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.0	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.8124	1	8.6990
2	2.2657	2	8.9334
3	1.8470	3	8.5660
4	2.2502	4	8.8629
5	1.9964	5	8.7893
6	2.2424	6	8.8899
7	1.8862	7	8.5385
8	2.2409	8	8.8511
9	1.9975	9	8.6046
10	2.0776	10	8.6299
11	2.1429	11	8.6917

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1497.99	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1559.42	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-37.70	-45.89	-35.07	-15.79	-41.16	-17.33	-44.63	-30.64	-33.86	-67.57	-97.05	-33.08	-36.22	-47.21	-20.37	-25.27	-16.28	-9.93	-51.12	-16.47
-51.87	-49.26	-70.05	-10.06	-61.58	-78.02	-54.69	-7.30	-74.63	-38.67	-22.73	-21.67	-45.75	-52.67	-44.11	-11.65	-4.37	-43.04	-42.66	-18.25
-32.91	-46.64	-35.47	-12.03	-42.28	-18.52	-51.21	-36.95	-33.60	-70.69	-102.7	-37.53	-34.48	-49.04	-16.29	-33.46	-12.89	-17.47	-50.67	-38.72
-49.90	-49.90	-69.23	-10.90	-60.71	-72.74	-52.64	-7.40	-71.69	-39.02	-23.09	-22.02	-45.47	-52.56	-46.74	-11.24	-4.65	-39.03	-42.87	-16.53
-211.2	-49.86	-33.33	-407.0	-23.68	-105.5	346.9	-183.8	3.99	-116.4	-82.78	-86.12	2.29	-60.20	14.53	-59.83	5.30	-36.02	-50.72	-83.76
-49.88	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.45	-55.96	-53.72	-8.10	-65.81	-40.98	-24.89	-24.43	-45.33	-53.37	-54.73	-12.55	-5.07	-31.53	-44.03	-19.60
-30.70	-49.26	-37.81	-8.77	-43.56	-18.38	-41.42	-24.29	-35.86	-66.16	-86.38	-37.66	-37.82	-49.15	-22.48	-25.69	-15.05	-8.43	-51.65	-10.75
-48.86	-54.84	-63.21	-13.49	-57.86	-45.64	-52.81	-8.79	-60.55	-43.10	-26.80	-27.33	-44.78	-53.86	-59.56	-13.73	-5.33	-26.11	-45.07	-21.57
-42.47	-52.29	-40.21	-18.32	-45.75	-20.41	-47.66	-21.00	-38.60	-64.48	-64.50	-44.03	-39.43	-51.19	-24.92	-27.97	-13.03	-11.46	-51.67	-19.85
-44.94	-57.90	-46.81	-19.95	-50.14	-25.46	-50.29	-14.34	-44.59	-55.63	-42.11	-48.14	-41.75	-53.43	-33.07	-23.50	-9.25	-14.45	-49.63	-25.63
-47.10	-58.50	-54.11	-17.25	-53.88	-32.53	-51.95	-10.92	-51.26	-48.57	-32.65	-36.40	-43.32	-54.02	-45.17	-17.98	-7.01	-18.62	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.83	-45.93	-36.05	-12.72	-41.34	-17.16	-47.86	-30.69	-38.12	-67.64	-96.96	-33.14	-98.56	-48.79	-20.91	-24.88	-16.54	-11.42	-104.5	-13.98
-72.84	-49.28	-71.04	-12.72	-61.64	-77.67	-58.91	-7.61	-79.07	-38.53	-22.76	-21.36	-120.3	-54.31	-45.26	-10.77	-5.36	-44.26	-99.29	-15.06
-70.04	-45.55	-35.87	-23.85	-40.44	-16.08	-39.76	-21.51	-38.98	-63.94	-104.0	-28.93	-105.6	-46.72	-26.07	-13.64	-21.91	18.56	-106.0	23.67
-75.18	-49.87	-70.35	-11.13	-61.02	-72.46	-61.11	-7.87	-76.74	-39.15	-23.28	-22.30	-119.4	-54.52	-47.55	-12.20	-4.92	-43.55	-99.29	-19.36
238.6	-47.36	-43.00	1096.	-63.68	68.55	-556.6	167.6	-113.	-19.84	-149.2	20.20	-250.1	-38.17	-66.45	21.53	-48.28	88.52	-117.2	97.89
-73.31	-52.42	-67.99	-12.72	-59.65	-55.94	-58.91	-8.13	-70.73	-41.16	-24.88	-24.72	-118.4	-55.23	-56.43	-12.92	-5.36	-33.55	-100.4	-19.36
-78.44	-49.35	-38.69	-39.74	-43.89	-19.23	-56.70	-25.71	-41.68	-67.10	-86.44	-40.19	-102.8	-51.53	-23.20	-30.62	-14.31	-22.13	-104.8	-30.12
-72.84	-54.82	-64.31	-14.31	-58.13	-45.62	-59.64	-8.92	-65.71	-43.32	-26.87	-27.67	-117.5	-55.76	-61.30	-14.59	-6.26	-28.55	-101.5	-23.67
-62.10	-52.28	-41.25	-19.08	-45.94	-20.42	-53.01	-21.25	-43.40	-64.63	-64.51	-44.71	-105.1	-52.94	-25.49	-28.71	-13.41	-14.99	-106.0	-20.44
-66.30	-57.88	-47.87	-20.67	-50.32	-25.42	-55.22	-14.43	-49.40	-55.75	-42.07	-49.23	-109.9	-55.18	-33.51	-23.92	-9.39	-17.85	-104.5	-25.82
-69.57	-58.50	-55.17	-19.08	-54.09	-32.59	-57.43	-11.28	-56.27	-48.80	-32.64	-36.82	-114.2	-55.89	-46.40	-18.42	-7.60	-22.13	-103.0	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.812	1	8.6990
2	2.266	2	8.9334
3	1.847	3	8.5660
4	2.250	4	8.8629
5	1.996	5	8.7893
6	2.242	6	8.8899
7	1.886	7	8.5385
8	2.241	8	8.8511
9	1.998	9	8.6046
10	2.078	10	8.6299
11	2.143	11	8.6917

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1497.99	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1559.42	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

For $H_{ref}=6,5$ m
Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.9	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.0	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.8	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.0	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5624	1	8.4490
2	2.0157	2	8.6834
3	1.5970	3	8.3160
4	2.0002	4	8.6129
5	1.7464	5	8.5393
6	1.9924	6	8.6399
7	1.6362	7	8.2885
8	1.9909	8	8.6011
9	1.7475	9	8.3546
10	1.8276	10	8.3799
11	1.8929	11	8.4417

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1371.23	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1280.68	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7080·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-37.80	-45.90	-35.06	-14.89	-41.16	-17.22	-44.40	-30.49	-33.95	-67.49	-87.57	-32.95	-36.36	-47.17	-20.27	-25.07	-16.34	-9.64	-51.14	-15.61
-45.57	-49.40	-70.00	-19.33	-61.19	-80.44	-45.88	-11.92	-73.77	-40.11	-21.06	-23.14	-44.78	-53.12	-42.94	-13.43	-3.56	-44.66	-42.57	-22.98
-44.02	-46.30	-35.64	-9.61	-42.67	-17.29	-64.42	-32.71	-35.84	-68.87	-100.2	-37.02	-37.64	-47.99	-25.24	-29.43	-19.48	-15.90	-51.26	-40.56
-49.11	-49.69	-69.30	-4.55	-60.75	-71.67	-53.95	-5.02	-72.05	-38.10	-20.46	-20.92	-45.91	-52.18	-47.39	-9.54	-5.16	-37.32	-42.92	-11.25
-279.3	-49.32	-40.43	-251.8	-47.02	-75.43	-91.54	-139.9	-42.52	-107.1	-134.8	-75.26	-36.84	-74.03	12.54	-150.5	21.44	-138.5	-48.00	-417.2
-49.80	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.47	-55.90	-54.12	-7.99	-65.97	-40.97	-22.31	-24.42	-45.35	-53.37	-54.75	-12.57	-5.07	-31.56	-44.03	-19.73
-35.66	-49.31	-37.76	-14.44	-43.54	-19.01	-42.28	-25.45	-35.98	-66.66	-81.74	-39.47	-37.79	-49.27	-22.64	-27.08	-14.18	-10.18	-51.49	-15.61
-49.14	-54.73	-63.31	-9.55	-57.98	-45.32	-53.84	-8.50	-60.74	-43.04	-24.31	-27.28	-44.83	-53.85	-59.61	-13.70	-5.35	-26.07	-45.07	-21.51
-42.59	-52.30	-40.22	-18.38	-45.75	-20.43	-47.66	-21.05	-38.72	-64.50	-59.25	-44.01	-39.42	-51.20	-24.94	-28.00	-13.06	-11.50	-51.67	-19.97
-44.68	-57.88	-46.80	-19.84	-50.13	-25.37	-50.23	-14.15	-44.70	-55.57	-40.10	-48.05	-41.73	-53.40	-33.07	-23.36	-9.25	-14.28	-49.63	-25.01
-46.95	-58.50	-54.11	-17.25	-53.88	-32.55	-51.83	-10.94	-51.38	-48.58	-30.17	-36.40	-43.32	-54.02	-45.17	-17.98	-7.04	-18.62	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.83	-45.92	-36.05	-14.31	-41.32	-17.16	-47.86	-30.69	-37.51	-67.64	-86.19	-33.24	-98.09	-48.79	-20.91	-25.12	-16.09	-12.14	-104.1	-15.06
-84.05	-49.15	-71.10	14.31	-62.05	-75.28	-70.69	-1.84	-80.17	-37.14	-19.49	-19.67	-124.1	-53.77	-46.69	-8.37	-6.71	-38.55	-100.0	-6.45
-49.49	-45.88	-35.68	-30.20	-40.06	-17.38	-23.56	-27.02	-34.81	-65.87	-97.98	-29.46	-93.35	-48.01	-15.18	-19.62	-11.62	12.14	-103.0	26.89
-76.11	-50.09	-70.27	-28.61	-60.99	-73.54	-59.64	-10.76	-75.64	-40.08	-19.11	-23.67	-117.9	-55.02	-46.98	-14.83	-4.47	-50.68	-98.92	-29.05
369.8	-48.01	-34.58	654.9	-39.97	38.56	6.63	113.3	-28.81	-29.34	-142.6	9.26	-109.9	-20.99	-65.02	155.9	-74.22	498.9	-132.8	680.9
-73.31	-52.42	-67.99	-12.72	-59.65	-55.94	-58.91	-8.39	-69.87	-41.16	-20.91	-24.72	-118.4	-55.23	-56.43	-12.92	-5.36	-33.55	-100.4	-19.36
-69.57	-49.31	-38.75	-25.44	-43.95	-18.68	-56.70	-24.40	-41.07	-66.72	-79.52	-38.29	-103.3	-51.41	-23.20	-28.71	-16.09	-15.71	-106.0	-22.59
-72.37	-54.95	-64.21	-25.44	-58.01	-45.95	-58.91	-9.44	-64.97	-43.40	-22.96	-27.77	-117.9	-55.81	-61.30	-14.83	-6.26	-29.27	-101.5	-24.74
-62.10	-52.28	-41.25	-19.08	-45.94	-20.42	-53.01	-21.25	-42.66	-64.63	-58.10	-44.71	-105.1	-52.94	-25.49	-28.47	-13.41	-14.99	-	106.0
																		1	-20.44
-66.77	-57.91	-47.88	-22.26	-50.35	-25.53	-55.96	-14.69	-48.79	-55.83	-38.60	-49.34	-110.4	-55.27	-33.80	-24.16	-9.39	-18.56	-104.8	-27.97
-70.04	-58.50	-55.17	-19.08	-54.09	-32.59	-57.43	-11.28	-55.53	-48.80	-28.92	-36.82	-113.7	-55.85	-46.40	-18.42	-7.60	-22.13	-103.0	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5492	1	8.4327
2	2.0219	2	8.6708
3	1.6354	3	8.2665
4	1.9858	4	8.6180
5	2.4301	5	7.9211
6	1.9888	6	8.6334
7	1.6254	7	8.2840
8	1.9860	8	8.5976
9	1.7405	9	8.3451
10	1.8237	10	8.3762
11	1.8894	11	8.4370

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1498.00	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1472.43	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7399·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

Run 3

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-38.34	-45.90	-35.06	-14.39	-41.17	-17.18	-44.14	-30.49	-33.80	-67.49	-97.27	-32.94	-36.22	-47.15	-20.38	-24.96	-16.31	-9.59	-51.13	-15.33
-51.80	-49.27	-70.04	-10.17	-61.57	-78.04	-54.61	-7.33	-74.63	-38.68	-22.80	-21.68	-45.74	-52.67	-44.11	-11.65	-4.37	-43.04	-42.66	-18.25
-39.14	-45.94	-35.27	-5.28	-41.46	-15.78	-45.83	-27.84	-33.93	-66.67	-103.5	-32.37	-36.13	-47.11	-19.03	-24.63	-15.19	-8.46	-50.93	-10.23
-49.83	-49.90	-69.23	-11.04	-60.70	-72.76	-52.52	-7.42	-71.68	-39.02	-23.14	-22.02	-45.45	-52.56	-46.74	-11.24	-4.64	-39.02	-42.86	-16.53
-66.54	-46.64	-36.96	39.79	-41.17	-10.91	8.12	-14.41	-29.20	-64.37	-106.2	-32.77	-32.46	-44.18	-26.25	3.09	-22.63	21.64	-53.48	84.77
-50.03	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.46	-55.95	-53.75	-8.09	-65.81	-40.98	-24.96	-24.42	-45.33	-53.36	-54.73	-12.55	-5.09	-31.53	-44.02	-19.60
-39.22	-49.33	-37.74	-17.56	-43.60	-19.10	-44.97	-25.42	-36.20	-66.72	-86.68	-38.60	-37.89	-49.53	-22.38	-27.65	-14.81	-10.59	-51.61	-17.94
-49.09	-54.83	-63.22	-13.18	-57.87	-45.59	-53.01	-8.72	-60.57	-43.09	-26.88	-27.31	-44.80	-53.85	-59.59	-13.73	-5.34	-26.10	-45.07	-21.57
-42.05	-52.29	-40.21	-18.38	-45.75	-20.41	-47.72	-21.01	-38.60	-64.48	-64.65	-44.04	-39.44	-51.20	-24.93	-27.98	-13.06	-11.46	-51.68	-19.85
-44.86	-57.90	-46.80	-20.03	-50.14	-25.47	-50.23	-14.36	-44.59	-55.63	-42.15	-48.14	-41.75	-53.43	-33.08	-23.51	-9.24	-14.45	-49.63	-25.60
-47.08	-58.50	-54.11	-17.22	-53.88	-32.53	-51.92	-10.92	-51.26	-48.57	-32.71	-36.39	-43.31	-54.02	-45.16	-17.98	-7.02	-18.63	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.13	-45.92	-36.06	-15.90	-41.33	-17.22	-48.60	-30.69	-38.25	-67.68	-96.61	-33.24	-98.56	-48.84	-20.77	-25.36	-16.32	-12.49	-104.3	-16.14
-73.07	-49.28	-71.05	-11.92	-61.65	-77.67	-59.27	-7.61	-79.19	-38.57	-22.67	-21.36	-120.5	-54.31	-45.26	-10.89	-5.36	-44.62	-99.48	-14.52
-57.20	-46.23	-36.12	-42.92	-41.27	-18.85	-46.76	-33.05	-38.43	-68.11	-103.	-34.87	-99.51	-49.08	-22.77	-26.68	-18.11	-17.85	-104.7	-25.82
-75.41	-49.87	-70.35	-10.33	-61.02	-72.46	-61.11	-7.74	-76.80	-39.15	-23.18	-22.36	-119.6	-54.52	-47.69	-12.20	-5.14	-43.55	-99.29	-19.36
-14.01	-50.78	-38.60	-172.4	-45.83	-25.85	-120.7	-42.37	-52.65	-73.28	-125.6	-41.08	-121.7	-57.69	-16.90	-70.70	-3.80	-140.9	-101.1	-194.7
-73.54	-52.42	-68.01	-13.51	-59.66	-56.00	-59.64	-8.39	-70.79	-41.20	-24.78	-24.78	-118.7	-55.27	-56.57	-13.16	-5.59	-34.27	-100.4	-20.44
-63.04	-49.28	-38.77	-15.90	-43.87	-18.58	-52.65	-24.40	-41.13	-66.60	-86.12	-39.19	-102.8	-51.08	-23.49	-27.87	-14.98	-13.92	-105.2	-18.29
-72.84	-54.84	-64.30	-15.10	-58.11	-45.62	-59.64	-9.18	-65.71	-43.32	-26.77	-27.72	-117.7	-55.76	-61.30	-14.71	-6.26	-29.27	-101.5	-23.67
-62.80	-52.28	-41.26	-19.08	-45.94	-20.37	-52.65	-21.12	-43.33	-64.63	-64.32	-44.71	-105.1	-52.94	-25.35	-28.59	-13.19	-14.63	-106.0	-20.44
-66.77	-57.89	-47.87	-20.67	-50.34	-25.42	-55.59	-14.43	-49.46	-55.75	-42.00	-49.23	-110.1	-55.20	-33.51	-23.92	-9.39	-17.49	-104.7	-26.36
-69.57	-58.50	-55.17	-18.28	-54.08	-32.53	-57.43	-11.15	-56.27	-48.76	-32.54	-36.82	-113.9	-55.87	-46.40	-18.42	-7.38	-21.77	-102.8	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5622	1	8.4486
2	2.0183	2	8.6811
3	1.5883	3	8.3251
4	1.9988	4	8.6142
5	1.6023	5	8.6829
6	1.9924	6	8.6403
7	1.6365	7	8.2885
8	1.9901	8	8.6021
9	1.7475	9	8.3541
10	1.8277	10	8.3795
11	1.8929	11	8.4418

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1498.00	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1464.07	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7390·10⁴	3.1254·10⁴

For $H_{ref}=6,75$ m

Optimum Results for the Dry Season

Pumping Well	Qopt1	Qopt2	Qopt3	Qopt4	Qopt5	Qopt6	Qopt7	Qopt8	Qopt9b	Qopt9a	Qopt11
1	392.55	237.96	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55
2	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63	8698.63
3	9683.17	10257.63	10257.63	7784.96	8161.91	10257.63	10257.63	10257.63	7804.13	7803.26	10257.63
4	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94
5	3474.58	3474.58	3474.58	3474.58	3474.58	2435.08	168.90	3474.58	3474.58	3474.58	1226.12
6	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	174.79	45.54	174.79	174.79	0.00	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79
8	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19
9	0.00	1498.00	1498.00	1498.00	1498.00	276.49	1498.00	1498.00	1498.00	1498.00	816.13
10	0.00	1334.78	1334.78	279.19	1334.78	0.00	1334.78	1334.78	165.98	178.27	1334.78
11	874.37	1559.42	1559.42	532.47	94.24	1301.42	387.17	1559.42	581.69	565.06	193.18
12	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19
13	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12
14	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60	1890.88	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60	2955.60
15	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64
16	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43
17	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78
18	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10
19	618.71	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13
20	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73
Total pumping rate	$3.2451 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7331 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7357 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2931 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2860 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3457 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3008 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7486 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2886 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2881 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3189 \cdot 10^4$

For $H_{ref}=7$ m

Optimum Results for the Dry Season

Pumping Well	Qopt1	Qopt2	Qopt3	Qopt4	Qopt5	Qopt6a	Qopt6b
1	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	0.00
2	8654.54	7134.81	8698.63	8698.63	7671.64	8698.63	8698.63
3	8990.56	10257.63	8901.43	8091.44	6360.73	10257.63	10257.63
4	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94
5	3474.58	0.00	3474.58	1828.31	3474.58	0.00	2422.00
6	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	0.00	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79	0.00
8	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19
9	0.00	422.38	1498.00	1498.00	1498.00	512.46	1498.00
10	0.00	0.00	1334.78	0.00	0.00	358.29	989.81
11	377.82	0.00	942.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19	1099.19
13	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12
14	0.00	2955.60	2955.60	0.00	2955.60	890.43	2955.60
15	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64
16	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43
17	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78
18	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10
19	0.00	1561.13	1561.13	1561.13	122.13	1561.13	1561.13
20	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73
Total pumping rate	$2.7644 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8303 \cdot 10^4$	$3.5512 \cdot 10^4$	$2.7824 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8229 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8425 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3961 \cdot 10^4$